

Analytical Applications of Ion-exchange Materials-II : Determination of Inorganic Ions by Precipitation Titrations

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Ferric phosphate inorganic ion exchanger granules are used as indicator in the determination of Ag(I), Hg(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Cu(II), Pb(II), Co(II), Ni(II), VO(II), UO₂(II) and Ce(IV). These ions can be determined in mg quantities with $\pm 1.00\%$ error in pure solution and in simultaneous determinations. Comparison of the proposed method with other known methods is discussed.

ION exchange resins have found some novel analytical applications in the detection and determination of organic functional groups¹⁻⁴. Funjimoto⁵ used resin beads as media for the detection of metal ions using known reactions. Resin beads loaded with indicators have also been used for the titration of acids and bases^{6,7}. Honda used such resin beads to estimate the pH in the resin phase⁸. Qureshi et al⁹ used resin beads in Fe(III) or *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine form as indicator in precipitation titrations with potassium ferrocyanide.

Inorganic ion exchangers show great selectivity towards certain metal ions and adsorb them irreversibly. Ferric phosphate adsorb Fe(III) irreversibly¹⁰, so this can be used more advantageously as both matrix and adsorbed Fe(III) ions can play combine effect to give sharp colour change at end point. Earlier studies were applied for the determination of thorium in presence of rare earths¹¹. In the present communication inorganic ion exchanger ferric phosphate is further used as indicator for the determination of various ions in pure form and in presence of other ions.

Experimental

Reagents

Potassium ferrocyanide : The trihydrate was dried at 100° for one hour. A 0.05M ferrocyanide solution was prepared by exact weighing and 1g of sodium carbonate was added per litre.

Silver nitrate, 0.05M
Vanadyl sulfate, 0.05M.

Ceric sulfate solution : Standardized against arsenious oxide.

Nitrates of other metal ions were used. Standard solutions were prepared by direct weighing from BDH 'Analar' grade reagents.

Resin beads : Dowex-50w-x8(20-50 mesh) resin beads in H⁺ form were soaked with *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine, for use in argentometric titration.

Ferric Phosphate Granules : Ferric phosphate granules were synthesized as in our earlier work¹⁰ were converted in H⁺ form and then soaked in ferric nitrate. Excess of ferric ions were washed with demineralized water.

Procedures :

Determination of Ag(I), Cu(II), Hg(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Pb(II), Co(II), Ni(II), VO(II), UO₂(II) and Ce(IV) : To the metal ion solutions were added 5 ml of 1M nitric acid (except in case of UO₂(II) and VO(II) where 10 ml of water was added) and 3 or 4 ferric phosphate granules in Fe³⁺ form. The solutions were titrated with potassium ferrocyanide from a 5 ml microburette. Near the end point the solution was vigorously shaken after the addition of each drop. A sharp colour change from white to blue on the granules appeared at end point owing to the formation of prussian blue. The results are given in Table 1.

Simultaneous determination of Ag(I) and Cu(II) : A silver nitrate, copper nitrate mixture was taken in a burette and added drop by drop to a known volume of sodium chloride solution containing resin beads in the *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine form. At equivalence point silver was precipitated as the chloride and copper nitrate remained in solution. A few drops of sodium chloride were added at the equivalence point to precipitate excess of silver (to minimize the error in the determination of copper), 10 ml of 1M nitric acid were added and copper was titrated with potassium ferrocyanide with Fe(III) form granules as indicator. The errors are from 0 to +0.09% for silver (1.35 to 5.40 mg) and 0 to +0.15% for copper (0.80 to 3.20 mg).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Ag(I), Hg(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Pb(II), Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), UO₂(II), VO(II) AND Ce(IV)

Taken (mg)	Amount of cations	
	Found (mg)	% Error
10.025 Hg(II)	10.048 Hg(II)	+0.22
2.506 Hg(II)	2.507 Hg(II)	+0.03
5.620 Cd(II)	5.642 Cd(II)	+0.39
1.405 Cd(II)	1.408 Cd(II)	+0.21
3.262 Zn(II)	3.278 Zn(II)	+0.30
0.817 Zn(II)	0.817 Zn(II)	0.00
10.359 Pb(II)	10.348 Pb(II)	-0.10
2.589 Pb(II)	2.594 Pb(II)	+0.19
3.177 Cu(II)	3.182 Cu(II)	+0.15
0.794 Cu(II)	0.794 Cu(II)	0.00
5.399 Ag(I)	5.408 Ag(I)	+0.28
1.348 Ag(I)	1.350 Ag(I)	+0.14
2.946 Co(II)	2.972 Co(II)	+0.88
0.786 Co(II)	2.972 Co(II)	0.00
2.935 Ni(II)	2.963 Ni(II)	+0.95
0.733 Ni(II)	0.730 Ni(II)	-0.40
13.500 UO ₂ (II)	13.592 UO ₂ (II)	+0.68
6.750 UO ₂ (II)	6.768 UO ₂ (II)	+0.38
3.375 UO ₂ (II)	3.380 UO ₂ (II)	+0.11
3.346 VO(II)	3.402 VO(II)	+1.70
1.673 VO(II)	1.680 VO(II)	+0.41
0.836 VO(II)	0.836 VO(II)	0.00
7.006 Ce(IV)	7.032 Ce(IV)	+0.37
3.503 Ce(IV)	3.511 Ce(IV)	+0.22
1.751 Ce(IV)	1.753 Ce(IV)	+0.11

Simultaneous determination of Ag(I) and Pb(II) :

The silver and lead were determined as above except in place of copper nitrate, lead nitrate was used. The errors are from 0 to +0.07% for silver (1.35 to 5.40 mg) and 0 to +0.03% for lead (2.60 to 10.370 mg).

Simultaneous determination of Ag(I) and Zn(II) :

The silver and zinc were determined as above except in place of copper nitrate, zinc nitrate was used. The errors are from 0 to +0.03% for silver (1.35 to 5.40 mg) and 0 to +0.09% for zinc (0.820 to 3.30 mg).

Simultaneous determination of Ag(I) and Cd(II) :

Same procedure was applied as above. The errors are from 0 to +0.05% for silver (1.35 to 5.40 mg) and 0 to +0.17% for cadmium (1.400 to 5.630 mg).

Simultaneous determination of Hg(II) and Zn(II) :

A mercury nitrate-zinc nitrate mixture was taken in a burette and added drop by drop to a known volume of iodide solution containing resin beads in the *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine form. At equivalence point mercury was precipitated as the iodide and zinc nitrate remained in solution. A few drops of potassium iodide were added at equivalence point to precipitate excess of mercury (to minimize the error in the determination of zinc), 10 ml of 1 M nitric acid were added and zinc was titrated with potassium ferrocyanide using Fe(III) from granules of ferric phosphate as indicator. The errors are from 0 to +0.13% for mercury (2.500 to 10.000 mg) and -0.24 to +0.12% for zinc (0.820 to 3.30 mg).

Successive determination of Zn(II) and I(I) : To a mixture of zinc nitrate and potassium nitrate a few beads of the resin in *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene-rhodanine form were added. The solution was titrated with mercury nitrate till a sharp colour change from yellow to violet on the resin was observed. A few drops of potassium iodide were added at equivalence point to precipitate excess of mercury (to minimize the error in the determination of zinc), 10 ml of 1M nitric acid and a few Fe(III) form granules of ferric phosphate were added then the zinc was titrated with potassium ferrocyanide. The errors are from -0.12 to +0.15% for zinc (0.820 to 3.300 mg) and -0.18 to +0.04% for iodide (1.600 to 6.340 mg).

Determination of Zn(II) in presence of Cd(II) :

To a mixture of zinc nitrate and cadmium nitrate 5.00 ml of potassium iodide (0.1M, to mask cadmium), 5.00 ml of 0.1M nitric acid and a few Fe(III) form ferric phosphate granules were added. As cadmium was masked by iodide, remaining zinc was titrated with potassium ferrocyanide till a sharp colour change from white to blue on the granules occurred at the end point. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Zn(II) IN PRESENCE OF Cd(II)

Taken (mg)	AMOUNT OF CATIONS	
	Found (mg)	% Error
5.620 Cd(II)+3.268 Zn(II)	3.276 Zn(II)	+0.24
5.620 Cd(II)+0.817 Zn(II)	0.815 Zn(II)	-0.24
28.100 Cd(II)+16.340 Zn(II)	16.351 Zn(II)	+0.06
56.200 Cd(II)+3.268 Zn(II)	3.279 Zn(II)	+0.33
84.300 Cd(II)+3.268 Zn(II)	3.283 Zn(II)	+0.45
5.620 Cd(II)+16.340 Zn(II)	16.324 Zn(II)	-0.09

Determination of Ce(IV) in presence of La(III) :

To a mixture of cerium sulphate and lanthanum nitrate, 5.00 ml of 0.1M nitric acid and a few Fe(III) form ferric phosphate granules were added. As lanthanum does not interfere, remaining cerium was titrated with potassium ferrocyanide till a sharp colour change from white to blue on the granules appeared at the end point and also the colour of the bulk solution sharply changed from yellow to green at end point. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF Ce(IV) IN PRESENCE OF La(III)

Taken (mg)	AMOUNT OF CATIONS	
	Found (mg)	% Error
6.945 La(III)+7.006 Ce(IV)	7.003 Ce(IV)	-0.04
13.890 La(III)+7.006 Ce(IV)	7.023 Ce(IV)	+0.24
20.835 La(III)+7.006 Ce(IV)	7.033 Ce(IV)	+0.38
34.725 La(III)+7.006 Ce(IV)	7.036 Ce(IV)	+0.42
69.450 La(III)+7.006 Ce(IV)	7.040 Ce(IV)	+0.48

Discussion

Ferric phosphate granules can be used as indicator for the determination of Ag(I), Zn(II), Hg(II) Cd(II),

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF THE RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED METHOD WITH THAT OF THE OTHER KNOWN METHODS

Metal ions	Proposed method		Other known methods ¹		Reference
	Range (mg)	% Error	Range	% Error	
Ag(I)	1.843–5.393	0 to +0.28	0.05–1 mg	± 5	(12)
Zn(II)	0.817–3.268	0 to +0.30	3.35–13.41 mg	0.8	(13)
Zn(II)	—	—	5×10^{-4} – $2 \times 10^{-2} M$	0.95	(14)
Cu(II)	0.794–3.177	0 to +0.15	3.21–9.62 mg	1.17	(13)
Hg(II)	2.506–10.025	+0.03 to +0.22	9.57–39.89 mg	1.5	(13)
Cd(II)	1.405–5.620	+0.21 to +0.39	2.770–2.825 mg	0.5	(15)
Cd(II)	—	—	5.41–21.63 mg	2.6	(13)
Ni(II)	0.733–2.935	–0.40 to +0.95	2.90–11.58 mg	4.9	(13)
Ni(II)	—	—	60–400 mg	2.0	(16)
Ni(II) in presence of Co(II)	0.733–14.675	–0.04 to +0.17	80–400 mg	1.9	(16)
Co(II)	—	—	—	—	—
Co(II)	0.736–2.946	0.00 to +0.88	60–400 mg	1.9	(16)
Co(II)	—	—	5×10^{-4} – $2 \times 10^{-2} M$	0.95	(14)
Ce(IV)	3.503–7.006	+0.22 to +0.37	1–30 mg	0.5–1.5	(17)
UO ₂ (II)	3.375–13.500	+0.11 to +0.68	10–100 mg	10	(18)

Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Pb(II), UO₂(II), VO(II) and Ce(IV) at low concentration where the precipitates are not very thick and the colour change can be marked easily. The percentage error is $< \pm 1.0$ for a single observation. Nearly in all cases the accuracy by the proposed method is more than the accuracy of other known methods. A comparison of the proposed method with other known methods can be represented in Table 4. It is clear from this table that the proposed method in general can be applied with greater accuracy.

Another novel feature is that granules can be used for successive determination of two substances. Thus zinc-iodide, silver-lead, silver-copper, silver-zinc and silver-cadmium mixtures can be determined without prior separation. This is feasible because it is possible to add different indicators in succession. This is not the case with conventional indicators.

Another advantage of ferric phosphate granule indicators is that a single indicator can be used when different species are titrated, with the same indicator. Thus all the metal ion reported have been titrated, using ferric phosphate granules in the Fe(III) form as indicator.

The method is based on the fact that when all the metal ions are precipitated a slight excess of ferrocyanide gives a sharp colour change to the granules from colourless to blue due to the formation of prussian blue.

Another important feature of this method is that cerium can be determined in presence of lanthanum and zinc can be determined in presence

of cadmium; thus no separation is required for the determination of these metals when present in the same solution.

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